

1. Collaboration is important for data access definition
2. Collaboration during data access definition may not happen
3. Collaboration may not help with data selection and model evaluation
4. Collaboration is important for ML artifact storage
5. Collaboration is important for ML model availability and integration
6. Collaboration is important for ML model deployment
7. Involving data scientists and business owners when eliciting and analyzing requirements can help with data access definition
8. Involving data scientists and business owners when eliciting and analyzing requirements may not help with data selection
9. Involving data scientists and business owners when eliciting and analyzing requirements can be useful for model evaluation
10. Involving data scientists and business owners when eliciting and analyzing requirements does not impact model integration and deployment
11. Involving data scientists and business owners when eliciting and analyzing requirements can impact model integration and deployment
12. Providing ML literacy for all project stakeholders may not be relevant for collaboration during data access definition
13. Providing ML literacy for all project stakeholders can be beneficial during data access definition
14. Providing ML literacy for all project stakeholders can be beneficial during ML artifact storage
15. Providing ML literacy for all project stakeholders can be beneficial during ML model deployment
16. Providing ML literacy for all project stakeholders can be beneficial during ML model integration
17. Developing documentation for product requirements, system architecture, and APIs at collaboration points may not be useful for data selection
18. Developing documentation for product requirements, system architecture, and APIs at collaboration points may be useful for model evaluation
19. Developing documentation for product requirements, system architecture, and APIs at collaboration points is important for model integration
20. Defining clear responsibilities and internal processes with clear boundaries for data scientists and software engineers is relevant for all tasks
21. Defining clear responsibilities and internal processes with clear boundaries for data scientists and software engineers is especially important for data scientists

22. Defining clear responsibilities and internal processes with clear boundaries for data scientists and software engineers may not be needed for model evaluation
23. Supporting interdisciplinarity between data scientists and software engineers may not be relevant
24. Supporting interdisciplinarity between data scientists and software engineers can be relevant during data access definition
25. Supporting interdisciplinarity between data scientists and software engineers can be relevant during data selection
26. Supporting interdisciplinarity between data scientists and software engineers can be relevant for model availability and integration
27. Supporting interdisciplinarity between data scientists and software engineers stimulates knowledge exchange
28. Organizing regular meetings for showcasing team activities is relevant to collaboration
29. Organizing regular meetings for showcasing team activities may not be relevant for all tasks